

Accessibility Guidelines for Deposits

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Slide deck checklist

Supporting resources:

- *Microsoft Accessibility Checker* tool built into Microsoft Office Suite (app only) with [additional documentation](#)¹ to aid its use. I recommend that slide decks created in other tools go through a final accessibility check with the Microsoft Accessibility Checker when possible.
- *Creating accessible Google Slides*, [a cohesive guide](#)² hosted by the Perkins School for the Blind, though some features listed are of limited availability.

1. Slide Structure:

- Use a logical and consistent slide structure, where slides are a balance of informative text and images, but not too image-heavy or too reliant on narrative explanation.
- Use slide titles and headings to organize content, ensuring that no slide titles are repeated. Slide titles can sit outside of the visible slide area to have this information present while not appearing on the slide itself.
- Ensure a clear reading order of elements, typically left to right and top to bottom, but whatever makes sense for as it will be presented. Reading order can be checked by tabbing through the slide or using accessibility checkers.
- When possible, use speaker notes for additional context and details. Licence information should be in the title slide rather than in the speaker notes.
- Specific for Google Slides:* Use a set template rather than building from scratch, as content within added textboxes are not guaranteed to be read by screen readers

2. Text Formatting:

- Use readable fonts, such as sans-serif (e.g., Arial, Calibri).

¹ 'Improve Accessibility with the Accessibility Checker - Microsoft Support'. n.d. Accessed 26 October 2023. <https://support.microsoft.com/en-gb/office/improve-accessibility-with-the-accessibility-checker-a16f6de0-2f39-4a2b-8bd8-5ad801426c7f>.

² Brauner, Diane. 'Creating Accessible Google Slides'. n.d. Accessed 3 July 2026. Perkins School for the Blind. <https://www.perkins.org/resource/creating-accessible-google-slides/>

- Use at least 24pt font size for body text, and headings at least 30pt.
- Use built-in bullets or numbered list features rather than manual formatting.
- Avoid using italics, underlines, or all caps for emphasis, as the proper formatting cannot be communicated to screen readers in slides like it can be for documents.

3. Colour and Contrast:

- Ensure text and background have sufficient colour contrast. A handy tool to test this is the [WebAIM Contrast Checker](#)³.
- *Specific for Microsoft Powerpoint*: The accessibility checker can assess contrast issues, but cannot check for contrast within imported images, only elements created within the software itself.
- When possible, check images used or generated for colour suitability with regards to colour vision deficiency (colour blindness). One online tool is [Vischeck](#)⁴, where images can be altered and you can download the altered image and use it (if the image licence allows).

4. Alternative Text for Images:

- Add descriptive alternative text to all images, charts, and graphics. For assistance on generating descriptive alternative text, refer to the [W3C Alt Decision Tree](#)⁵.
- *Specific for Microsoft Powerpoint*: Use Microsoft Accessibility Checker to ensure images have appropriate alt text, including any that may have AI-generated alt text or incorrectly attributed alt text.
- *Specific for Microsoft Powerpoint*: Where appropriate, designate decorative elements using the “Mark as decorative” feature in the Alt text dialogue box for images and visual elements or groupings.
- *Specific for Google Slides*: There is no way to mark images as decorative; any images without alt-text/image description are read as “Image” by screen readers.

5. Hyperlinks:

- Use descriptive hyperlink text (e.g., "Read more about accessibility" instead of "Click here").

³ WebAIM. n.d. 'WebAIM Contrast Checker'. Accessed 03 July 2026. <https://webaim.org/resources/contrastchecker/>

⁴ 'Vischeck'. Accessed 03 July 2026. <https://www.vischeck.com/index.html>

⁵ 'W3C Web Accessibility'. n.d. 'An Alt Decision Tree'. Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI). Accessed 03 July 2026. <https://www.w3.org/WAI/tutorials/images/decision-tree/>.

- Ensure that hyperlinks are distinguishable and not solely reliant on colour, such as by underlining the hyperlink.
6. Multimedia and Audio:
- Provide transcripts and captions for audio and video content.
7. Multiple File Formats for Dissemination/Publishing:
- Specific for Microsoft Powerpoint:* A final check with the accessibility checker, export as PDF (Use “Export” option rather than print as PDF to ensure accessible properties are included) and then save as an open format of choice (such as .odp). These three formats (.pdf, .pptx, and .odp) can be uploaded to the same repository entry, where the .pdf is the stable, reference version.
 - Specific for Google Slides:* A final Accessibility Check in Microsoft PowerPoint is recommended as many features will not be available in Google-exported formats.

Further References:

Karcher, Sebastian, Theresa Anderson, Randy Colon, and Abigail Goben. 2022. ‘Slides for: Curating for Accessibility’. Presented at the IDCC 2022, June 15.

<https://zenodo.org/records/6644046>.

University Library Klagenfurt. n.d. ‘Accessible Media – Accessibility Services, University Library Klagenfurt’. *University Library Klagenfurt* (blog). Accessed 03 July 2026.

<https://www.aau.at/en/university-library-klagenfurt/use-and-service/accessibility-services/accessible-media/>.

Document checklist

Supporting resources:

- *Microsoft Accessibility Checker* tool built into Microsoft Office Suite (app only) with [additional documentation](#)⁶ to aid its use.
- *Create Accessible Google Docs*⁷, a webpage created and hosted by the Digital Accessibility Services at Harvard University alongside an example Google Doc that walks through some of the settings referenced.

1. Document Formatting:

- Use proper headings (Title, Heading 1, Heading 2, etc.) for document sections to create a clear hierarchy. This can be adjusted in the Styles menu in Microsoft Word and Google Docs.
- Use lists (bulleted or numbered) to organize content instead of manual formatting.
- Specify the document language in the document properties to assist screen readers (Tools menu of Microsoft Word and File menu of Google Docs).
- Use Table of Contents tools rather than drafting manually.

2. Text Formatting:

- Use sans-serif fonts (e.g., Arial or Calibri) for improved readability.
- Ensure text is at least 12pt for body text and 18pt for headings.
- Avoid underlining text as it can be confused with hyperlinks.
- Use the Style options of Strong or Emphasis for highlighting content instead of bold and italic – they look the same, but the Style options include additional formatting that informs screen readers and document ordering.
- So-called “hidden text” (e.g. text in white font on white background) will be read by screen readers.

3. Table Formatting:

- For each table used, the header row needs to be defined and captions should be used for data tables.
- Avoid using both empty and merged cells in tables, as this complicates table navigation.

⁶ 'Improve Accessibility with the Accessibility Checker - Microsoft Support'. n.d. Accessed 03 July 2026. <https://support.microsoft.com/en-gb/office/improve-accessibility-with-the-accessibility-checker-a16f6de0-2f39-4a2b-8bd8-5ad801426c7f>.

⁷ Harvard University. n.d. 'Create Accessible Google Docs'. Digital Accessibility Services (Harvard University). Accessed 03 July 2026. <https://accessibility.huit.harvard.edu/google-docs>.

4. Images:

- Add descriptive alternative text to all images, charts, and graphics. For assistance on generating descriptive alternative text, refer to the [W3C Alt Decision Tree](#)⁸.
- Ideally, images are inserted “In Line with Text”
- Specific for Microsoft Word*: Use Microsoft Accessibility Checker to ensure images have appropriate alt text, including any that may have AI-generated alt text or incorrectly attributed alt text.
- Specific for Microsoft Word*: Where appropriate, designate decorative elements using the “Mark as decorative” feature in the Alt text dialogue box for images and visual elements or groupings.
- Specific for Google Docs*: There is no way to mark images as decorative; any images without alt-text/image description are read as “Image” by screen readers.

5. Hyperlinks:

- Use descriptive hyperlink text (e.g., "Read more about accessibility" instead of "Click here").
- Ensure that hyperlinks are distinguishable and not solely reliant on colour, such as with underlining.

6. Colour Contrast and Colour Choice:

- Ensure text and background have sufficient colour contrast. A handy tool to test this is the [WebAIM Contrast Checker](#)⁹.
- Specific for Microsoft Word*: The accessibility checker can assess contrast issues, but cannot check for contrast within imported images, only elements created within the software itself.
- When possible, check images used or generated for colour suitability with regards to colour vision deficiency (colour blindness). One online tool is [Vischeck](#)¹⁰, where images can be assessed and altered and you can download the altered image and use it (if the image licence allows).

7. Multiple File Formats for Dissemination/Publishing:

- Specific for Microsoft Word*: after a final check with the Accessibility Checker, export as PDF (Use “Save As” or “Save a Copy” option rather

⁸ Initiative (WAI), W3C Web Accessibility. n.d. ‘An Alt Decision Tree’. Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI). Accessed 03 July 2026. <https://www.w3.org/WAI/tutorials/images/decision-tree/>.

⁹ WebAIM. n.d. ‘WebAIM Contrast Checker’. Accessed 03 July 2026. <https://webaim.org/resources/contrastchecker/>

¹⁰ ‘Vischeck’. Accessed 03 July 2026. <https://www.vischeck.com/index.html>

than print as PDF to ensure accessible properties are included) as well as open format of choice (.rtf, .odt). These three formats (.pdf, .docx or .doc, and .odt or .rtf) can be uploaded to the same repository entry, where the .pdf is the stable, reference version.

- *Specific for Google Docs*: A final Accessibility Check in Microsoft Word along with advice above is recommended as many features will not be available in Google-exported formats – PDFs from Google Docs will require much more effort in PDF tools to make them minimally accessible.

Further References:

Blumesberger, Susanne, Sonja Edler, Eva Gergely, Doris Haslinger, and Denise Trieb. 2022. 'Guidelines on Preparing Accessible Content for Repositories: Format PDF'. <https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/o:1594526>. <https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/detail/o:1594526>.

Karcher, Sebastian, Theresa Anderson, Randy Colon, and Abigail Goben. 2022. 'Slides for: Curating for Accessibility'. Presented at the IDCC 2022, June 15. <https://zenodo.org/records/6644046>.